

Whole-genome sequencing of a halotolerant *Rhodococcoides sp.* strain isolated from soil in Argentina with plant growth-promoting traits

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Abstract

We report the complete genome sequence of *Rhodococcoides sp.* strain M4-66 which was isolated from an agricultural lot located at the southeastern area of Cordoba Province, Argentina, and exhibited *in vitro* halotolerance and plant growth-promoting (PGPR) capabilities. Whole-genome sequencing of this strain was performed to investigate genes associated with PGPR activities, as well as those involved in stress tolerance, including osmotic adaptation and oxidative stress responses. Its halotolerance and PGPR potential were also evaluated through *in vitro* assays. The genome was sequenced using Illumina NovaSeq 6000 and assembled with SPAdes v. 3.7. The genome consists of a single circular chromosome of approximately 4.078.612 bp, with a GC content of 70.2%. The genome provides insights into the genetic basis of the PGPR traits observed *in vitro* for this *Rhodococcoides* strain: nitrogen fixation, phosphate solubilization and cellulolytic activity. PGPR bacteria represents a useful resource for the development of sustainable strategies to enhance crop productivity in stressed environments through environmentally friendly solutions. Genomic sequences were deposited in NCBI GenBank under the BioProject PRJNA1230365.

Introduction

Modern agriculture is facing challenges driven by climate change, soil degradation, and the growing demand to ensure food security in an environmentally sustainable way. In this context, regenerative agriculture has emerged as a holistic approach that aims to restore soil health, promote biodiversity, and increase the resilience of agricultural systems (LaCanne & Lundgren, 2018; Giller et al., 2021). Within this paradigm, plant growth-promoting rhizobacteria (PGPR)

play a key role due to their ability to enhance crop performance in a natural and sustainable manner.

PGPR can exert multiple beneficial effects on plants, including biological nitrogen fixation, phosphate solubilization, phytohormone production, and the induction of systemic tolerance to various biotic and abiotic stresses (Spaepen et al., 2009; Puga-Freitas et al., 2015; Bhattacharyya and Jha, 2012). These properties make them valuable allies in the development of agroecological strategies that reduce reliance on synthetic inputs and improve resource-use efficiency. Plant growth promotion is accomplished by three main strategies: biostimulation, biofertilization, and bioprotection, or a combination thereof. Biostimulation results from the secretion of plant hormones by the microbes themselves, directly affecting hormone levels and signaling in the plant host. The strongest growth-promoting effect is attributed to the secretion of auxin that affects the root system, but bacterial production of ethylene, cytokinin, gibberellin, and abscisic acid has been implicated as well (Cassan et al., 2014). Additionally, a multitude of microorganisms can modulate hormone levels and signaling in the plant by secreting enzymes that influence phytohormone metabolism, such as 1-amino-cyclopropane-1-carboxylic acid (ACC) deaminase (Glick, 2014). Biofertilization leads to an improved nutritional status of the plant and enhances the nutrient availability in the rhizosphere, especially of iron, nitrogen, and phosphorus (Pii et al., 2015). Bioprotection or biocontrol, when microbes offer plants protection against pathogens, can be accomplished by diverse mechanisms, including aggressive colonization of the plant roots, production of antagonistic compounds, such as antibiotics and hydrogen cyanide, interference with quorum sensing-controlled processes in pathogens, and/or activation of induced systemic resistance in the plant (Etesami, 2024).

In the current scenario—marked by extreme weather events, soil salinization, and water scarcity—it is crucial to deepen our scientific understanding of the biotechnological potential of PGPR strains adapted to harsh environments. Their strategic use, grounded in solid scientific evidence and tailored to local agroecosystems, can significantly contribute to crop resilience and the success of regenerative production models. Stress-tolerant, plant-associated bacteria play an important role in protecting plants against abiotic stresses, and members of the genus *Rhodococcoides*, known for their stress tolerance, are frequently found in the plant microbiome (Francis et al., 2016). To determine the genetic bases of the growth-promoting effect, the chromosome of *Rhodococcoides* sp. M4-66 was mined for genes possibly involved in stress tolerance, including those related to osmotic adaptation and oxidative stress response, as well as the genes related to PGPR activities, biostimulation and biofertilization.

Materials and Methods

Bacterial Isolation

The bacterial strain was isolated from a soil with CE = 1.3 mS/cm, pH 8 and 9 ppm P. The site is characterized by the presence of halophytic vegetation, including *Salicornia* sp. and *Distichlis*

spicata. Efforts aiming to improve soil conditions for the cultivation of *Medicago sativa* were carried out in the past.

DNA Processing

Five to forty microliters of the cell suspension are lysed with 120 μ L of TE buffer containing lysozyme (final concentration 0.1 mg/mL) and RNase A (ITW Reagents, Barcelona, Spain) (final concentration 0.1 mg/mL), incubated for 25 min at 37°C. Proteinase K (VWR Chemicals, Ohio, USA) (final concentration 0.1 mg/mL) and SDS (Sigma-Aldrich, Missouri, USA) (final concentration 0.5% v/v) are added and incubated for 5 min at 65°C. Genomic DNA is purified using an equal volume of SPRI beads and resuspended in EB buffer (10 mM Tris-HCl, pH 8.0). DNA extracted by MicrobesNG, or sent directly by the customer is then quantified with the Quant-iT dsDNA HS kit (ThermoFisher Scientific) assay in an Eppendorf AF2200 plate reader (Eppendorf UK Ltd, United Kingdom) and diluted as appropriate.

Illumina Sequencing

Genomic DNA libraries are prepared using the Nextera XT Library Prep Kit (Illumina, San Diego, USA) following the manufacturer's protocol with the following modifications: input DNA is increased 2-fold, and PCR elongation time is increased to 45 seconds. DNA quantification and library preparation are carried out on a Hamilton Microlab STAR automated liquid handling system (Hamilton Bonaduz AG, Switzerland). Libraries are sequenced on an Illumina NovaSeq 6000 (Illumina, San Diego, USA) using a 250 bp paired end protocol. Reads are adapter trimmed using Trimmomatic version 0.30 (Bolger et al., 2014) with a sliding window quality cutoff of Q15. De novo assembly is performed on samples using SPAdes version 3.7 (Bankevich et al., 2012), and contigs are annotated using Prokka 1.11 (Seeman, 2014).

In vitro assessment of halotolerance and PGPR-related activities

Halotolerance of the isolate was evaluated by culturing it on nutrient agar (NA) supplemented with increasing NaCl concentrations (1.2, 2.3, 3.5 and 6%) following Principe et al. (2007). The presence of key functional microbial groups, including cellulolytic bacteria, ammonifiers, and nitrifiers, was assessed using the most probable number (MPN) technique in specific liquid media, as described by Abril (2003). Free-living nitrogen-fixing microorganisms were quantified by the pour plate method. For this, 10 g of each sample were homogenized in 90 mL of sterile peptone water (0.1 g/100 mL). Bacteria capable of nitrogen fixation were cultured in nitrogen-free medium for five days at 28–30 °C, according to Abril et al., (2010). The phosphate-solubilizing capacity of each strain was determined following Frioni (1999), using an optimized medium containing yeast extract (2 g L⁻¹), glucose (20 g L⁻¹), and Ca₃(PO₄)₂ (2 g L⁻¹). NA plates supplemented with this medium were inoculated with 10 μ L of each pure bacterial culture (1 \times 10⁹ CFU mL⁻¹). Five replicate plates were incubated aerobically at 28–30 °C for seven days. Phosphate solubilization was indicated by the formation of clear halos around the colonies.

Results

Genome sequencing and assembly

Trimmed sequence read data and genome assembly data of the *Rhodococoides sp.* M4-66 strain has been deposited in NCBI/GenBank under the BioProject PRJNA1230365. A summary of the genome features are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Summary statistics of *Rhodococoides sp.* M4-66 strain isolated from soil in Argentina

Organism	<i>Rhodococoides sp.</i>
Host	Soil
Genome size	4.078.612 bp
Number of contigs	12
Contig N50	703.246 bp
Mean coverage	138x
GC Content	70.2 %
BioProject ID	PRJNA1230365
BioSample ID	SAMN47177064
GenBank Accession (Assembly)	ASM4853803v1
GenBank Accession (Reads)	SRR32539092

In vitro assessment of halotolerance and related genes

The isolated strain exhibited halotolerance, being able to grow in media supplemented with up to 6% (w/v) NaCl. Genomic analysis revealed the presence of genes related to choline and betaine uptake, betaine biosynthesis and general osmoregulation. Additionally, a total of 15 genes associated with oxidative stress were identified, including genes involved in non-redox glutathione-related processes, glutaredoxins, oxidative stress response proteins, glutathione biosynthesis, the gamma-glutamyl cycle and the glutathione redox cycle. These genetic traits support the observed halotolerant phenotype of the strain.

In vitro assessment of PGPR activities and related genes

Regarding the observed PGPR activities, the strain was able to fix atmospheric nitrogen, solubilize phosphate, and exhibited cellulolytic activity. The associated genes identified included *nifH* (nitrogen fixation), *phoA* and *phoD* (involved in phosphate solubilization and iron uptake), and several genes associated with cellulolytic activity (*celA*, *celB*, *bglX*, *xynA*, *man*, among others). Although siderophore activity was not tested in vitro, the complete *entA-F* gene cluster

related to enterobactin biosynthesis (a siderophore involved in iron acquisition) was found, suggesting that this strain would exhibit this activity.

Acknowledgements

The sequencing of the bacterial strain was supported by GetGenome and The Sainsbury Laboratory, Norwich, UK, which support from the Gatsby Charitable Foundation and the Biotechnology and Biological Sciences Research Council (BBSRC).

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